

References

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having cell dimensions $a=9.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$, $V=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$, $\rho=2.3003 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $n=1$; where (Dan. Van) and (Dan. Sal) stand for phenolic OH deprotonated Schiff bases.

Experimental

The experimental details, elemental analyses, ir spectral data, conductivity values have already been reported in the earlier communication¹. The X-ray data were recorded on a Phillips PW 1050/70 machine attached with a diffractogram. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ at $5-80^\circ (2\theta)$ using the scale $1^\circ=1 \text{ cm}$.

X-Ray Diffraction Studies of some Thorium(IV) Schiff Base Complexes

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IN continuation to our investigation¹ on thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (Dan) with vanalline (van) and salicylaldehyde (sal), we report herein the powder X-ray diffraction data for the complex $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ having cell dimensions $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$, $V=300.91 \text{ \AA}^3$, $\rho=4.3258 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $n=1$, and the complex $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ correspond to the molecular formulae as $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{NO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, respectively. The diffractograms record 7 reflections for the first and 11 reflections for the second compound between 5 and $80^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta=44.75^\circ$ for the first and $2\theta=23.8^\circ$ for the second which correspond to $d=2.0205 \text{ \AA}$ and $d=3.700 \text{ \AA}$, respectively. The 2θ values for prominent peaks are listed in Table 1. All main peaks have been indexed^{2,3} and their $\sin^2\theta$ values compared with the calculated ones. Comparison of the values reveals a good agreement between the calculated and observed values of $\sin^2\theta$. The unit cell has been calculated by the

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA OF Th^{IV} COMPLEXES

Peak no.	d	Relative intensity $\times 100 I/I_0$	Observed $\sin^2 \theta$	Calculated $\sin^2 \theta$	(hkl)	2θ
(i) $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Van})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$						
1	3.228 5	61.8	0.056 40	0.052 82	200	27.50
2	2.353 3	56.4	0.107 0	0.105 6	220	38.25
3	2.020 5	65.4	0.145 2	0.145 2	311	44.75
4	1.482 2	29.0	0.269 9	0.237 7	420	62.50
5	1.437 1	32.6	0.237 1	0.239 8	332	64.75
6	1.282 5	29.0	0.360 5	0.356 6	333	73.80
7	1.220 9	34.4	0.397 6	0.396 1	521	78.10
(ii) $[\text{Th}(\text{Dan. Sal})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$						
1	5.601	74.4	0.018 3	0.018 45	110	15.55
2	4.650	85.4	0.027 75	0.027 67	111	19.17
3	3.700	100.0	0.042 5	0.042 95	210	23.80
4	2.804	32.10	0.075 15	0.073 79	220	31.90
5	2.657	31.20	0.083 98	0.083 01	300	33.70
6	2.172	26.30	0.125 7	0.123 1	321	41.55
7	2.029	29.00	0.144 0	0.147 6	004	44.60
8	2.003 6	29.00	0.147 7	0.147 6	404	45.20
9	1.729	23.6	0.198	0.198 7	332	52.90
10	1.646	12.8	0.218 9	0.221 4	422	55.80
11	1.538	18.2	0.250 7	0.249 1	511	60.10

For complex-I (cubic system): $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$, $V=309.11 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt.=784, density (ρ) (calcd.)= 4.3258 g cm^{-3} , $n=1$, density (obs.)= 4.3479 g cm^{-3} . For complex-II (tetragonal system): $a=8.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$, $V=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$, mol. wt.=722, density (ρ) (calcd.)= 2.3033 g cm^{-3} , $n=1$, density (obs.)= 2.3275 g cm^{-3} . For cubic system: $a^3 = \frac{\lambda^3 (h^3 + k^3 + l^3)}{4 \sin^2 \theta}$; for tetragonal

system: $\sin^2 \theta = \frac{\lambda^2}{4} \left[\frac{h^2}{a^2} + \frac{k^2}{a^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \right]$.

trial and error method⁴⁻⁶. The observed values fit well in cubic system to give a unit cell with lattice constants $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=300.91 \text{ \AA}^3$ for the first complex and in tetragonal system to give a unit cell with lattice constant $a=8.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$ for the second complex. Substitution of this cell volume primitive lattice ($n=1$) for the first complex gives the theoretical value of density equal to 4.3258 g cm^{-3} and substitution of cell volume primitive lattice ($n=1$) for the second complex gives the theoretical value of density equal to 2.3003 g cm^{-3} . The experimental values of densities of the two complexes have been found to be 4.3479 and 2.3275 g cm^{-3} which are fairly in good agreement within the limits of experimental errors.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of $(OCN)_2$ - $Co(NCSHgR)_2$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5) and $L_2(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ (L =methanol, pyridine or nicotinamide)

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WITH a view to study bonding mode of cyanate and thiocyanate, $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ where $R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5 and their adducts with methanol(MeOH), pyridine(py) and nicotinamide(nia) were prepared. The effect of steric hindrance, caused by organic groups attached to Hg^{II} , has been studied on the bonding mode of cyanate and thiocyanate groups.

Experimental

All materials and manipulations were done as reported earlier¹.

Preparation of complexes: $Co(NCO)_2L_4$ ($L=py, nia$) and $RHgCl$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5) were prepared according to literature methods²⁻⁶. Methylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the metathesis of mercury thiocyanate and dimethylmercury as described earlier⁶. Ethylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the reaction of ethylmercury chloride and potassium thiocyanate in acetone in 1 : 1 molar ratio, on stirring for 1 h. The filtrate after removal of precipitated potassium chloride was concentrated by evaporation under reduced pressure. C_2H_5HgSCN was precipitated by water from the concentrate, which was filtered, washed with water and dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure. It was recrystallised from ethanol and dried in vacuum oven at 50° .

Butylmercury thiocyanate was prepared similarly. Phenylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the method reported earlier⁷. $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgCH_3)_2$ was prepared by stirring ethanolic solution of $Co(NCO)_2$ (1 mmol) and CH_3HgSCN (2 mmol), for ~ 36 h. The precipitated blue compound was filtered, washed with ethyl acetate and dried under reduced pressure. Ethyl, n-butyl and phenylmercury thiocyanate derivatives were similarly prepared.

$(Py)_2(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ were similarly prepared by stirring acetone solution of $Co(NCO)_2 \cdot 4py$ (1 mmol) in different flasks for ~ 36 h. The resulting pink complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from acetone and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . Nicotinamide complexes were prepared similarly. Methanol complexes were prepared by stirring acetone solutions of $RHgSCN$ (2 mmol) with methanol solutions of $Co(NCO)_2$ in different flasks for ~ 48 h. The resulting pink complexes were filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

Alternatively, all complexes could also be prepared by stirring suspensions of Lewis acids, $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$, and ligands in separate flasks in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio for ~ 36 h.

Cobalt was estimated as cobalt anthranilate, sulphur as barium sulphate and mercury as mercury sulphide, gravimetrically. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Molar conductance values of $0.001 M$ solutions in DMF, and molecular weights in DMSO (freezing point depression method) and room temperature magnetic moment values are presented in Table 1. Ir ($4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), far-ir ($500-50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and uv-visible ($2500-200 \text{ nm}$) spectra were recorded as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

Lewis acids: $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5): The positions of ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} , ν_{HgC} , δ_{SCN} and ν_{HgS} observed at about 2180,